

Formulae for comparison of Copenhagen simulation results with theoretical predictions

L. Lidgren 79-10-16 (ESTEC)

1. Notations

n_{star} = number of stars on the sky

n_{scan} = number of scans

$n_{\text{scans/star}}$ = number of scans (average) during which a particular star is observed

$n_{\text{stars/scan}}$ = number of stars in the strip of the sky ~~covered~~ covered by one scan

$n_{\text{stars/frame}}$ = average number of stars simultaneously in the combined FOV

n_{obs} = total number of grid-coordinate observations (case of "instantaneous directions")

$n_{\text{angles/scan}}$ = number of angle measurements per scan (case of ~~"pair observations"~~ "pair observations")

Φ = FOV size, i.e. angle along one of the sides of the square FOV (rad)

τ = mission duration in years

R = number of scans per day

ξ = revolving angle (from sun to z axis)

K = no. of revolutions around sun per year

w_2 = average speed of z axis on sky due to revolving law (rad/yr)

σ_H, σ_ξ = m.e. of grid coordinate measurements (marsec)

σ_a = m.e. of angle measurement (marsec)

σ_x = m.e. of star abscissa (per scan) (marsec)

$F_\beta, F_\lambda, F_{\mu\beta}, F_{\mu\lambda}, F_{\omega}$ = improvement factors (step 3) for $\beta, \lambda, \mu\beta, \mu\lambda, \omega$.

Q_{frame} = fractional overlap of successive frames

Q_{scan} = fractional overlap of successive scans (at antinodes)

2. Basic relations between different numbers

Since the solid angle of the combined FOV is $2\Phi^2$ (approx), we have

$$n_{\text{stars/frame}} = \frac{\Phi^2}{2\pi} n_{\text{star}} \tag{1}$$

The fraction of the sky covered by one scan is $\sin \frac{\Phi}{2} \approx \frac{1}{2} \Phi$;

thus
$$n_{\text{stars/scan}} = \frac{1}{2} \Phi n_{\text{star}} \tag{2}$$

The number of scans is

$$n_{\text{scan}} = 365 R \tau \tag{3}$$

In order to have overlap by Q_{scan} on successive scans, we must have

$$\frac{1}{365 R} \omega_2 = (1 - Q_{\text{scan}}) \Phi ; \tag{4}$$

hence

$$n_{\text{scan}} = \frac{\omega_2 \tau}{(1 - Q_{\text{scan}}) \Phi} \tag{5}$$

Since $\frac{\Phi}{2}$ is the probability that an arbitrary (given) star is in the strip of the sky covered by a scan, the average number of scans during which the star is seen is

$$n_{\text{scans/star}} = \frac{\Phi}{2} n_{\text{scan}} = \frac{\omega_2 \tau}{2(1 - Q_{\text{scan}})} \tag{6}$$

We note that the speed ω_2 of the z axis in the sky is given by

$$\omega_2 = 2\pi \left[1 + \left(K^2 - \frac{1}{2} \right) \sin^2 \xi \right]^{1/2} \tag{7}$$

and is $\omega_2 \approx 28$ rad/yr almost independent of ξ , if $K = 270^\circ / \xi$. Thus, if $Q_{\text{scan}} = 0.5$, we have $n_{\text{scan/star}} \approx 20\tau$, independent of Φ , n_{star} , ξ , etc.

The total number of observations is (one obs. per star per frame): (3)

$$n_{obs} = n_{stars/frame} \cdot n_{frames/scan} \cdot n_{scan} \quad (8)$$

W.R. overlap Q_{frame} in successive frames, we have

$$n_{frames/scan} = \frac{2\pi}{(1-Q_{frame})\Phi}, \quad (9)$$

which, combined with (1) and (5) gives us

$$n_{obs} = \frac{\omega_2 \tau}{(1-Q_{scan})(1-Q_{frame})} n_{star}. \quad (10)$$

Eqs. (8)-(10) refer to the case of "instantaneous directions" observation. If we make angle measurements between pairs of stars, we assume the smallest number of angle measurements. This is obtained by connecting each star image to each of the $n_{stars/frame}$ stars (within an angle Φ ahead on the great circle. Since there are $2n_{stars/scan}$ images per scan, we have

$$\begin{aligned} n_{angles/scan} &= 2n_{stars/scan} \cdot n_{stars/frame} \\ &= \frac{\Phi^2}{2\pi} n_{star}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

and the total number of angle measurements is

$$n_{angles} = n_{scan} \cdot n_{angles/scan} = \frac{\omega_2 \tau}{(1-Q_{scan})} \frac{\Phi^2}{2\pi} n_{star}^2 \quad (12)$$

3. Relation between abscissa me. and σ_η

Let T be the total time available for observation per scan, and let $\sigma(t) = \sigma_0 t^{-1/2}$ be the me. of a grid coordinate after integration over a time t . (for stars of average magnitude).

Consider first the measurement of instantaneous directions.

Since the number of observations per scan is

$$n_{\text{obs/scan}} = n_{\text{obs}} / n_{\text{scan}} = \frac{\Phi}{(1 - \alpha_{\text{plane}})} n_{\text{star}}, \quad (13)$$

The time available for each observation is $T / n_{\text{obs/scan}}$ and consequently

$$\sigma_{\eta} = \sigma_0 \left(\frac{T}{n_{\text{obs/scan}}} \right)^{-1/2} = \sigma_0 T^{-1/2} \sqrt{\frac{\Phi n_{\text{star}}}{1 - \alpha_{\text{plane}}}} \quad (14)$$

Turning now to angle measurements we have the available time per angle measurement $T / n_{\text{angles/scan}}$; this time is divided between the two stars in the pair, who receive $T / 2 n_{\text{angles/scan}}$ each. Thus their grid coordinates are determined to m.e. $\sigma = \sigma_0 (T / 2 n_{\text{angles/scan}})^{-1/2}$ and the m.e. of the angle between them is $\sigma_a = \sqrt{\sigma^2 + \sigma^2} = \sqrt{2} \sigma$ or

$$\sigma_a = 2 \sigma_0 T^{-1/2} (n_{\text{angles/scan}})^{+1/2} \quad (15)$$

According to ESTEC report, section 3.8.3, the abscissa m.e. is then given by

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x &= \sigma_a \cdot \sqrt{\frac{u n_{\text{stars/scan}}}{2 n_{\text{angles/scan}}}} \\ &= 2 \sigma_0 T^{-1/2} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} u n_{\text{stars/scan}}} \\ &= \sigma_0 T^{-1/2} \sqrt{2 u \cdot \frac{1}{2} \Phi n_{\text{star}}} \\ &= \sigma_0 T^{-1/2} \sqrt{u \Phi n_{\text{star}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $u \approx 1.7$ according to 3.8.3.

Comparison of (16) and (14) gives the relation between σ_η and σ_α :

$$\sigma_\alpha = \sqrt{(1 - Q_{frame})} U \sigma_\eta \tag{17}$$

With $Q_{frame} = 0.5$ and $U = 1.70$ we have $\sigma_\alpha \approx 0.922 \sigma_\eta$.

4. Influence of σ_ξ

The result (17) neglects the attitude uncertainty, reflected mainly by σ_ξ . In fact the measurement of ξ enters in two different ways in the stick solution: firstly, it determines the attitude around the x and y axes, and therefore the necessary projection factors for reducing grid coordinates η to angles along the reference great circle. Secondly, if σ_ξ is comparable with σ_η , it contributes direct information on the astrometric parameters, especially on the parallax, if ξ is relatively small (since the parallax displacements are $\Delta\eta \propto \sin \xi$ and $\Delta S \propto \cos \xi$). However, in practice $\sigma_\xi \gg \sigma_\eta$ and the second effect is then probably negligible.

The attitude error which goes into the angle or grid coordinate measurement is $\Delta\varphi \approx \cos \varphi_2 \Delta\lambda_2 \cos \beta_2 - \sin \varphi_2 \Delta\beta_2$ (ESTEC report, section 3.8). This is a rotation around either optical axis. If a frame contains one star from each FOV, the rotation around the two optical axes are fixed (in each field) by the ξ -measurement in

the other field. Since the basic angle is less than 90° , we may expect the m.e. of the rotation component of each field to be approximately

$$\sigma_\varphi = \sigma_\gamma / \sin \gamma. \quad (?) \quad (18)$$

Eq. (3.8.10) of the ESTEC report then gives an expression for the angle measurement m.e. and hence the abscissa m.e.:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_d^2 &= \frac{U n_{\text{stars/scan}}}{2 n_{\text{angles/scan}}} \cdot \sigma_a^2(0) + (\Delta S_{\text{rms}})^2 \frac{\sigma_\gamma^2}{\sin^2 \gamma} \cdot \frac{U n_{\text{stars/scan}}}{2 n_{\text{angles/scan}}} = \\ &= (1 - Q_{\text{frame}}) U \sigma_\gamma^2 + \frac{\pi U}{12 \sin^2 \gamma} \frac{1}{n_{\text{star}}} \sigma_\gamma^2 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $\sigma_a(0)$ is the angle m.e. in case $\sigma_\gamma = 0$, i.e. from (17), and we have used

$$(\Delta S_{\text{rms}})^2 = \frac{1}{6} \Phi^2, \quad (20)$$

assuming that the stars are uniformly distributed in $\gamma \in [-\frac{\Phi}{2}, \frac{\Phi}{2}]$, and also the relation

$$\frac{n_{\text{stars/scan}}}{n_{\text{angles/scan}}} = \frac{\pi}{\Phi^2 n_{\text{star}}}. \quad (21)$$

Eq. (19), with $Q_{\text{frame}} = 0.5$, $U = 1.70$, $\gamma = 68.5^\circ$, is the only formula required for computing σ_d for the different simulations. It is quite remarkable that Φ and several other parameters does not at all enter ~~the~~ the formula!

5. Coefficients of improvement

Analysis of the various computations of F_0 by myself, AML and Vaghi shows that the coefficients (after averaging over the sky) depend very little on K (as long as $K \geq 270^\circ/5$), initial conditions, uniform or non-uniform scanning, or symmetric versus asymmetric scanning. In fact, the only parameters which are of importance are ξ and the ~~the~~ average number of scans per star ($n_{scans/star}$) and (for proper motions only) the mission duration τ . Thus we have in fact to sufficient accuracy the simple relations

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 F_\beta &= 1.26 (\cos \xi)^{-1/2} (n_{scans/star})^{-1/2} \\
 F_\lambda &= 1.55 (\sin \xi)^{-1/2} (n_{scans/star})^{-1/2} \\
 F_{\mu\beta} &= \frac{\sqrt{12}}{\tau} F_\beta \\
 F_{\mu\lambda} &= \frac{\sqrt{12}}{\tau} F_\lambda \\
 F_w &= 0.80 (\sin \xi)^{-1} (n_{scans/star})^{-1/2}
 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (23)$$

The numerical factors 1.26, 1.55, and 0.80 are averages derived from the numerical experiments referred to above. The factor $\sqrt{12}/\tau$ for p_{μ} is theoretical (assuming uniform distribution of observations in time $t \in [0, \tau]$), but is verified within a few percent by the numerical experiments. — It should be noted that the fractional dead time f is not included in (23) or any of the formulas thus far; the correction factor for m.e. is of course $(1-f)^{-1/2}$.

The m.e. of astrometric parameters are then $\sigma_\alpha \cdot F_i (1-f)^{-1/2}$.

6. Comparison of theoretical results with Copenhagen simulations

Parameters: $\Delta scan = \Delta frame = 0.5$, $\omega_2 \approx 28 \Rightarrow n_{scan/star} \approx 28\tau$.

The table below gives the estimated m.e. σ_β , σ_λ and σ_w from (19) + (23); numbers in parentheses are corresponding results from simulation experiments. (* = average over $|\beta| = 20^\circ - 40^\circ$ only.)

Experiment (Fig. no. in Hoyer et al. 79-10-04)	n_{stars}	τ	ξ	σ_η	σ_ζ	σ_α	σ_β	σ_λ	σ_w		
				----- msecsec -----							
4b. 15°	2	200	26	0.5	30°	10	100	10.52	3.81	6.16	
									(4.1)	(6.7)	
4c. 15°	2	200	26	0.5	40°	10	100	10.52	4.05	5.44	
									(3.9)	(5.2)	
5a. 30°	2	50	13	1.0	30°	10	100	13.70	3.51	5.68	4.14
									(3.1)	(5.3)	(4.7)
5b. 15°	2	200	26	1.0	30°	10	100	10.52	2.69	4.36	3.18
									(2.7)	(4.8)	(4.2)
6a. 30°	2	50	13	0.5	20°	10	100	13.70	4.76	9.70	
									(4.6)*	(12.0)*	
6c. 10°	2	450	39	0.5	30°	10	100	9.82	3.55	5.75	
									(4.0)*	(7.1)*	
6c. 10°	2	450	39	0.5	40°	10	100	9.82	3.78	5.07	
									(4.0)*	(5.5)*	
7a-c. 30°	4	100	26	1.0	30°	10	100	11.68	2.99	4.84	3.53
									(2.3)	(3.2)	(3.4)
10a-c. 30°	2	50	13	1.0	30°	10	1000	101.8	26.1	42.2	30.8
									(6.5)	(13)	(13)

Average factor: $\frac{\text{experimental m.e.}}{\text{theoretical m.e.}}$ (excluding 10a-c.): 0.98 1.05 1.14
 (dispersion) $\pm 0.11 \pm 0.16 \pm 0.18$

The results of the experiments with $\sigma_\zeta = 1''$ (10a-c) show that eq. (19) probably overestimates the influence of σ_ζ . Disregarding this experiment, there is a very good general agreement between the predicted m.e. and the m.e. found from the simulations. This shows that the basic principles used for estimating the m.e. of the astrometric parameters are probably correct.